

Original Research

From Global Context To Regional Action: Assessing Poverty Reduction In Southern Africa

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Abstract

Over the years, poverty has been a persistent, multifaceted challenge in many countries worldwide, especially in developing countries. This paper uses Southern African Development Community (SADC) as a case study to assess poverty reduction, from a global context to the Southern African context. The central research question addresses how socio-economic factors contribute towards poverty within the global and Southern African contexts. This is followed by a second research question that examines efforts that can contribute to sustainable poverty reduction. The study employed a qualitative methodology, collecting data from primary sources such as official government documents, newspaper articles, and official websites. Secondary data was gathered from books, journal articles, case studies, and evaluation reports. The research examines the factors that continue to perpetuate poverty, including climate change, corruption, political instability, armed conflicts, disease burdens, colonial legacies, failure to collaborate and digital inequality. Findings position Regional Economic Communities (RECs) as significant tool for promoting regional integration, cooperation and development between countries. The study recommends integrating Ubuntu principles—such as solidarity, mutual responsibility, and human dignity—into policy frameworks across SADC member states to promote nation-building and prioritize collective well-being. SADC should also invest in introducing new farming technologies and improved market access for small-scale agriculture to address food insecurity and unemployment, especially among marginalized groups across the region.

Keywords: SADC; Poverty reduction; RECs;Poverty; Regional Integration**Introduction**

In one of his famous speeches, Nelson Mandela stated that “As long as poverty, injustice and gross inequality persist in our world, none of us can truly rest”.¹

Poverty is a prevalent challenge in many countries across Africa. Globally, significant progress has been made towards reducing poverty. However, progress has been relatively unattainable in the Southern Africa region. Moatsos and Lazopoulos argue that global poverty is characterized by severe scarcity of economic resources.² While Bush posit that poverty thrives when individuals are deprived of access to essential opportunities to advance human development.³ Additionally, financial institutions define extreme poverty by the number of people living on less than \$2.15 per day for low-income countries,⁴ \$3.65 for lower-middle-income countries, and \$6.85 for upper-middle-income countries.⁵

¹ Simon Jeffery, “Mandela Calls For Action on ‘Unnatural poverty’,” *Gurdian*, 3 February, 2005, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2005/feb/03/hearfrica05.development>

² Michail Moatsos, Achillefs Lazopoulos, “Global poverty: A First Estimation Of Its Uncertainty,” *World Development Perspectives* 22,(2021): 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wdp.2021.100315>

³ Ray Bush, *Poverty and Neoliberalism: Persistence and Reproduction In The Global South* (London: Pluto Press,2007),2.

⁴ “Measuring Poverty,” World Bank Group, 2024, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/measuringpoverty>

Furthermore, other scholars contend that poverty should not be viewed solely in terms of material deprivation. Instead, it is also a phenomenon that affects a society's cultural and social characteristics, which in turn, hinder development.⁶ Hence, Spitzer and Twikinize argue that the state of poverty does not only refer to lack of finances but rather to a broader context that affects people's capabilities, their integrity and dignity.⁷

Global poverty in the early 90's was measured using the DAD approach, which estimates poverty lines based on national poverty lines (NPLs) from the least economically developed countries. Therefore, a particular poverty line, which is the international poverty line, captures the level of poverty across the world at large.⁸ For many years, countries across the world have been working towards global poverty reduction. However, in the mid-20s, low-income countries experienced an increase in poverty due to various crises and shocks, further hindering their ability to recover and close the existing poverty gap.⁹

In this regard, regional integration emerged as a key instrument for enhancing economic cooperation and fostering international relations worldwide.¹⁰ The 1980s marked a period when the establishment of regional economic blocs became central to promoting economic growth and development of countries.¹¹ Hence, African states under the umbrella of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) converged with the mandate of promoting economic cooperation, culminating in signing of the Abuja Treaty in 1991, to establish the African Economic Community (AEC).¹² In an effort to address poverty across the Southern Africa region, the front-line states of Angola, Botswana, Mozambique, Tanzania, and Zambia convened in July 1979 to discuss the formation of the Southern African Development Coordination Conference (SADCC). Organized by Botswana's first president, Seretse Khama, the meeting centered on promoting economic cooperation and political liberation for Southern African nations, as well as reducing economic dependence on apartheid-era South Africa.¹³

In this regard, regional integration emerged as a significant element in fostering international relations between countries worldwide.¹⁴ The 1980s saw the rise of regional economic blocs as vital tools for fostering economic growth and development. During this period, African countries, operating under the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), united to advance economic cooperation. This collaboration culminated in the signing of the Abuja Treaty in 1991, which laid the foundation for the African Economic Community (AEC).¹⁵ In line with this framework, the Southern African Development Community (SADC) was later established under the OAU Abuja plans with the intention of advancing regional integration and development in the Southern African region.¹⁶ This affirmed that the regional bloc formed a part of the African Union (AU)'s Regional Economic Communities (RECs).¹⁷ SADC regional economic bloc implements development in Southern Africa under the guidance of the African Union (AU), advancing development through political cooperation, eradicating poverty and maintaining peace and stability.¹⁸ Nonetheless, despite all efforts, SADC's poverty alleviation initiatives have setbacks limiting the regional bloc's effectiveness in attaining development across its member states.¹⁹

This article examines historical and political factors that have contributed to poverty from a global perspective, focusing on Southern Africa. In this context, various foundational factors that underpin poverty will be unpacked. Additionally, the establishment of regional blocs will be discussed to demonstrate how regional integration has played a crucial role in achieving poverty reduction across Southern Africa and globally. The study further provides insight

⁵ "Poverty, Prosperity, and Planet Report," World Bank, https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/poverty-prosperity-and-planet?cid=PUB_GA_wbpublications_EN_EXTP_3PR&gclid=Cj0KCCQias5i8BhDmARIsAGE4xHyZbCrVrO2FMMyMCZAvH89XiIUxk1lGA7e2RJ3wuKK0Xr4YfBrGDiaIaAruXEALw_wcB

⁶ Vertegen, Suzanne. *Poverty and Conflict: An Entitlement Perspective*. Brussels: Conflict Prevention Network, 2001

⁷ Helmut Spitzer, M Twikirize, G.G Wairire, *Professional Social Work in East Africa: Towards Social Development, Poverty Reduction and Gender Equality* (Kampala: Fountain Publishers, 2014), 39.

⁸ Michail Moatsos, Achillefs Lazopoulos, "Global poverty: A First Estimation of Its Uncertainty," *World Development Perspectives* 22, (2021): 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wdp.2021.100315>

⁹ "Understanding Poverty," World Bank Group, accessed August 18, 2024, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/understanding-poverty>

¹⁰ Maurice W. Schiff, Alan Winters, *Regional Integration and Development* (Washington DC: World Bank and Oxford University Press, 2003), 1-2.

¹¹ Kalenga, Paul. "Regional integration in SADC: Retreating or forging ahead." *Trade Law Centre (TRALAC)*, South Africa (2012).

¹² Kalenga, *Regional Intergration*.

¹³ Reginald Herbold Green, "Southern African Development Coordination: Toward a Functioning Dynamic?," *Institute of Development Studies* 11, no.4:53. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/286046042.pdf>

¹⁴ Maurice W. Schiff, Alan Winters, *Regional Integration and Development* (Washington DC: World Bank and Oxford University Press, 2003), 1-2.

¹⁵ Kalenga, Paul. "Regional integration in SADC: Retreating or forging ahead." *Trade Law Centre (TRALAC)*, South Africa (2012).

¹⁶ "SADC and African Union," Southern African Development Community, 2022, <https://www.sadc.int/pages/sadc-african-union>

¹⁷ "SADC and African Union,"

¹⁸ "SADC and African Union,"

¹⁹ P A Brynard, "Policies and Poverty in Southern Africa," *African Journal of Public Affairs* 4, no.1 (2011):9-10.

<https://repository.up.ac.za/server/api/core/bitstreams/a6d9fa7b-cdc1-44ad-bf55-d61db55e35f4/content>
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into how policies introduced by Regional Economic Communities (RECs), such as the Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the European Union (EU), have been instrumental in achieving poverty reduction. Consequently, the success of these RECs enables the Southern African Development Community (SADC) to benchmark and promote development in the Southern African region. Furthermore the study is guided by Capability Theory and Ubuntu, which together provide a framework for evaluating both individual wellbeing and collective development.

Literature Review

From a global perspective, poverty has affected a number of countries, subsequently causing severe impacts on people livelihoods.²⁰ However, Ng et al argue that for decades the global struggle against the multi-faceted phenomenon has been defined by various factors.²¹ Despite that thousands of people have been pulled out of extreme poverty, driven by fast economic growth in emerging economies, there still exists the constant and troubling reality of continuous social, political, economic, climate issues causing the prevalence of poverty in the society.²² Martuscelli argues that rapid economic growth became possible through the establishment of regional economic blocs across the world, making poverty reduction and advancement of development achievable.²³ The milestone of establishing regional economic blocs stood out to signify regional integration as a significant component which can be incorporated in solving poverty crisis across the world.²⁴

Meggitt observes that people living in poverty are primarily preoccupied with physical survival, which is predominantly a form of material poverty. This condition is marked by limited access to essential needs such as clothing, food, and shelter, thus confining their lives to a subsistence level in stark contrast to the experiences of the wealthy.²⁵ Korankye argues that poverty should be viewed as a violation of human rights.²⁶ Therefore, it is the responsibility of governments and various societal stakeholders to ensure that the needs of people living in poverty are addressed. By promoting equality and working to narrow the gap between the rich and the poor, they can contribute to a more just and inclusive society.²⁷

Poverty encompasses a range of attributes that vary across countries and have evolved over time. As a multidimensional phenomenon, poverty can be characterized by factors such as unemployment, insufficient income, illiteracy, inadequate food, malnutrition, high mortality and morbidity rates, limited access to clean water and sanitation, vulnerability to natural disasters or economic shocks, powerlessness, lack of representation, and restricted freedom. These dimensions have been the subject of extensive debate among scholars and policymakers globally. Despite the longstanding international focus on poverty reduction, a consensus on how to measure poverty has not been achieved. According to Toye, poverty reduction is often assessed by counting the number of people living on less than one dollar per day. However, this approach can be adapted to local contexts by using the equivalent value in local currency for countries in Southern Africa, thereby measuring the population's purchasing power parity more accurately.²⁸ Scholars have debated the importance of poverty reduction for development, especially in low-income countries, including those in Southern Africa, which are among the most severely affected by poverty.

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in Capability theory and Ubuntu philosophy, which both advocate human development and promote the wellbeing of communities, their cooperation, and their advancement, all of which are vital for poverty reduction. Ubuntu emphasizes solidarity and cooperation of communities towards collective advancement and development. Through the principle of "motho ke motho ka batho", the Tswana language or 'umuntu ngubuntu ngabantu', the Nguni language, which translates to 'a person is person through other people'; Ubuntu agrees that Africans should handle their problems in a positive enthusiastic manner through incorporating humanistic values

²⁰ Mitchel Chossudovsky, *Organizational Studies: Critical Perspective on Business and Management* (London: Routledge, 2001), 77.

²¹ Alex Hou Hong Ng, Abdul Ghani Farinda, Fock Kui Kan, Ai Ling Lim, Teo Ming Ting, "Poverty: Its Causes and Solutions," *International Journal of Business, Human and Social Sciences* 7, no. 8 (2013): 2471.

²² Ng et al., "Poverty: Its Causes and Solutions," 2472.

²³ Antonio Martuscelli, "Regional Intergration and Poverty: A Review of The Transmission Channels and The Evidence," *Journal of Economic Surveys* 33, no. 2 (2018): 431-433. <https://repository.up.ac.za/server/api/core/bitstreams/a6d9fa7b-cdc1-44ad-bf55-d61db55e35f4/content>

²⁴ Martuscelli, "Regional Intergration and Poverty," 434.

²⁵ Justin Meggitt, Paul, *Poverty and Survival* (Edinburgh: T&T Clark, 1998), 5.

²⁶ Alex Addae-Korankye, "Causes of Poverty in Africa: A Review of Literature," *American International Journal of Social Science* 3, no. 7 (2014): 148. https://www.aijssnet.com/journals/Vol_3_No_7_December_2014/16.pdf

²⁷ Addae-Korankye, "Causes of Poverty in Africa", 149.

²⁸ John Toye, "Poverty reduction," *Development in Practice* 17, no. 4-5 (August 2007): 508. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614520701469427> .

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adapted from their ancestors and history.²⁹ In addition it carries a significant foundation within the traditions of Bantu-speaking people of Southern Africa as it promotes peace building, conflict resolution, and social solidarity. Kuhumba suggests that Ubuntu encourages communities to take responsibility for human development, enabling policies related to education, healthcare, social freedom, economic freedom, and political freedom to more effectively address people's needs. Therefore, when people work collectively by embracing Ubuntu principles, it fosters peace, stability, and economic development within society.³⁰

The capability theory focuses on individuals as the position of addressing poverty, while the possession of some of the capabilities consists of relating to systems, and other people in a society.³¹ The capability approach holds a central role in development and social justice. Additionally, it is seen as a normative and evaluative framework that describes development as the expansion of individuals' substantive freedoms to achieve lives they have reason to value.³² Moreover, the theory does not solely focus on income levels, it examines whether individuals can achieve core functioning such as being educated, healthy, adequately nourished, and socially included. This enables the identification of underlying forms of deprivation that income-based measures often miss, such as lack of access to healthcare, exclusion from political participation, or access to education opportunities.³³ In this manner, the theory emphasizes human agency, ensuring that individuals have the power to make meaningful choices and participate in decisions affecting their lives. In this sense, poverty is not only material deprivation but also a lack of empowerment, representation, and voice.³⁴

Materials and Methods

Using a case study research method, this study assesses poverty from global context and Southern African contexts, particularly using SADC as a case study. The case study method is suited to this study, as it offers a deeper understanding of various issues by providing valuable insights into life at multiple levels—individual, institutional, and community.³⁵ Moreover, it enables analysis of public policy matters that are particularly significant for poverty reduction in Southern Africa.³⁶

The study employed qualitative research approach, by utilising primary sources, including official government documents, newspaper articles, and official websites, which provide direct and contemporaneous evidence of policies, decisions, and public discourse, allowing for an accurate understanding of policy intentions and implementation contexts. While secondary data was gathered from books, journal articles, case studies, and evaluation reports from organisations such as SADC, the United Nations (UNDP, UNICEF, and World Food Programme), the World Bank, and the African Union to contextualize findings, support critical analysis, and engage with existing scholarship. By drawing on these diverse materials, the research provides a comprehensive analysis and enables well-founded conclusions about specific programs and policy interventions. Furthermore, the qualitative method incorporates the use of archives and media sources to offer detailed descriptions and analyses of policies initiated by SADC aimed at poverty reduction in its member states.³⁷

Results and Discussions

The findings of the study highlight that Southern Africa countries comprise different economic statuses and backgrounds due to various factors such as wars, colonial legacies, climate shocks and political instability, which subsequently contribute towards poverty across the Southern Africa region.³⁸ Hence Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) has formulated policies towards poverty reduction in the region.³⁹

Legacy of Apartheid and Poverty

²⁹ John Hailey, *Ubuntu: A Literature Review* (London:2008),

<https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=5af48f144b75fd4662b36934e26b52bdf0629e97>

³⁰ Shija Kuhumba, "Amartya Sen's Capability Approach As Theoretical Foundation of Human Development," *Journal of Sociology and Development* 1, no. 1: p.128-129.

³¹ Serena Cosgrove, Benjamin Curtis, *Understanding Global Poverty: Causes, Solutions, and Capabilities* (New York: Routledge, 2022), 5.

³² Cosgrove and Curtis, *Understanding Global Poverty*, 6.

³³ Ingrid Robeyns, "The Capability Approach: An Interdisciplinary Introduction." 3rd International Conference on The Capability Approach: Netherlands, 9 December, https://commonweb.unifr.ch/artsdean/pub/gestens/f/as/files/4760/24995_105422.pdf.

³⁴ Robeyns, "The Capability Approach,"

³⁵ Available at <https://egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/11227/1/Unit-14.pdf>

³⁶ Catherine Cassell, Gillian Symon, *Essential Guide to Qualitative Methods in Organizational Research* (London: Sage Publishers, 2004), 323-324.

³⁷ Sharan B. Merriam, Elizabeth J. Tisdell, *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation* (San Francisco: Jossey-Bass, 2016), 158.

³⁸ Available at <https://www.sadc.int/document/regional-poverty-reduction-framework>

³⁹ "The Regional Poverty Reduction Framework."

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Reddy argues that colonialism in Southern Africa manifested in multiple forms, notably in a form of settler colonialism, as seen under apartheid had profound and lasting effects on society and economy. During this period, the white settler minority systematically oppressed and discriminated the black majority through land dispossession, physical violence, and perpetuating economic exploitation through the imposition of cheap labour, entrenching structural inequalities. These policies produced lasting effects on the region's social and economic structures.⁴⁰ He additionally states that many black people in South Africa endured the harsh effects with countless lives lost during the apartheid regime. Moreover, communities were pushed into deep poverty, promoting inequality and discrimination across the population at large. Consequently, apartheid entrenched a legacy of economic marginalization and inequality that continues to shape contemporary South African Society.⁴¹

Rural poverty and urban migration are deeply intertwined in South Africa. Limited economic opportunities in rural areas driven by inadequate infrastructure, low agricultural productivity, and constrained access to education and healthcare—trap many communities in persistent cycles of poverty. These hardships compel individuals and families to migrate to urban places in search of improved livelihoods. However, rapid urbanization frequently outpaces job creation and development of adequate housing, leading to the expansion of informal settlements and entrenched urban poverty. This pattern highlights the enduring effects rooted in the legacy of Apartheid, which systematically marginalized rural populations and restricted their access to essential resources, thereby perpetuating socio-economic disparities between rural and urban communities.⁴²

Makgetla contends that South Africa is amongst the most unequal countries in the world.⁴³ Despite the formal end of the apartheid regime in 1994, the country continues to operate under a two-tiered economy, with one that is highly developed while the other is under-resourced.⁴⁴ Therefore, this has perpetuated chronic racial disparities, contributing to an increase in unemployment, particularly amongst black people.⁴⁵

Xenophobic practices in South Africa have generated fear in the society, as well as endangering people's lives.⁴⁶ Moreover, discrimination has fueled negative stereotypes against foreigners living in South Africa. Migrants from Zimbabwe, Nigeria, and Somalia often face severe discrimination, including attacks on their homes and businesses, leaving many homeless and socially marginalized.⁴⁷

Climate Change

Climate change represents a significant threat to the development of countries in Southern Africa.⁴⁸ With drought emerging as one of the primary drivers of poverty. In 2023, countries such as Botswana, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Lesotho, and Madagascar were severely affected by the El Niño phenomenon.⁴⁹ As a result, these countries experienced extremely high temperatures and delayed rainfall, leading to widespread drought across various parts of the region undermining agricultural productivity and escalating food insecurity.⁵⁰ This contributed to increased poverty in Southern African communities, as climate change-related challenges intensified pre-existing socio-economic vulnerabilities.⁵¹ Mozambique, in particular, is one of the Southern African countries drastically prone to climate change effects due to its geographical location, often experiencing cyclones, droughts, and floods, all of which directly affect people's livelihoods.⁵² Moreover, the cumulative effects of climate change have severely impacted numerous

⁴⁰ Thiven Reddy, *South Africa, Settler Colonialism and The Failures of Liberal Democracy* (London: Zed Books, 2015), 5.

⁴¹ Lephakga, "Colonial Institutionalisation of Poverty," 13.

⁴² Julian May, "Poverty Eradication: The South African Experience," Paper prepared for Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Division for Social Policy and Development and Economic Commission for Africa, Economic Development and NEPAD Division Expert Group Meeting on Poverty Eradication, 2010, <https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/social/meetings/egm10/documents/May%20paper.pdf>

⁴³ Neva Makgetla, "Inequality in South Africa: An Overview," Working Paper, (Trade and Industrial Policy Strategies, 2020), https://tips.org.za/images/TIPS_Working_Paper_Inequality_in_South_Africa_An_Overview_September_2020.pdf

⁴⁴ Liz Sonneborn, *The End of Apartheid in South Africa* (New York: Infobase Publishing, 2010), 11.

⁴⁵ Ian Shapiro, Kahreen Tebeau, *After Apartheid: Reinventing South Africa?* (London: University of Virginia Press, 2011), 21-22.

⁴⁶ Jean Pierre Misago, Iriann Freemantle, Loren B. Landau, *Protection From Xenophobia: An Evaluation of UNHCR'S Regional Office for Southern Africa's Xenophobia Related Programmes* (Johannesburg: African Centre for Migration and Society, 2015), <https://www.unhcr.org/sites/default/files/legacy-pdf/55cb153f9.pdf>

⁴⁷ David Everatt, "Xenophobia, State and Society in South Africa, 2008- 2010," *South African Journal of Political Studies* 38, no.1(2011):8-10. https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/02589346.2011.548662?casa_token=FM4VTZL8OhMAAAAAA:5BjUZDVXtoVWZIxL-t4jZtOkdedCHSFUzJdlwvJJA5y68X6PwYINBhx7HKCc78M3wgbgocUxzi

⁴⁸ Lesley Masters, Lyndsey Duff, *Overcoming Barriers to Climate Change Adaptation Implementation In Southern Africa* (Braamfotein: 2017), 183.

⁴⁹ *Regional Report 2024 On the State of Food and Nutrition Security and Vulnerability in Southern Africa*, Gaborone: Southern African Development Community, 2024

⁵⁰ Southern African Development Community, *Regional Report 2024 on the State of Food and Nutrition Security and Vulnerability in Southern Africa*.

⁵¹ SADC, *Regional Report 2024 on the State of Food and Nutrition Security*.

⁵² Ange-Benjamin Brida, Tom Owiyo, Youba Sokona, "Loss And Damage From The Double Blow Of Flood And Drought In Mozambique, " *International Journal of Global Warming* 5, no.4(2013):516.

districts in Mozambique, leading to widespread of hunger, starvation, and undernourishment, with children disproportionately affected, highlighting the need for adaptation of resilience strategies.⁵³

Cambaza and others state that in 2019, the strongest cyclone ever recorded in Africa struck Mozambique, leading to a widespread outbreak of cholera across the country.⁵⁴ In early March 2023, approximately 166,600 people in Mozambique's Inhambane province were severely affected by heavy rainfall, which destroyed more than 12,700 homes and damaged crop yields on about 38,100 hectares of land. As a result, many were left homeless and without access to basic necessities.⁵⁵ Moreover, the country's healthcare system further deteriorated, particularly in rural areas along the coastline.⁵⁶ Climate change has also had a significant impact on Lesotho, where more than 75 percent of the population lives below the poverty line. The majority of people depend on seasonal rainfall for agriculture, making them especially vulnerable to climate variability.⁵⁷ However, climate change effects such as El Niño have resulted in widespread severe drought, leading to increased food insecurity and severe hunger among the population.⁵⁸ Widespread food insecurity remains a persistent challenge, particularly affecting marginalised groups, children, and people living with HIV/AIDS.⁵⁹

Political Instability

Political instability is a critical determinant of poverty in Southern Africa. Finnegan explains that Mozambique is among the countries currently experiencing severe poverty—a condition that has persisted since its independence from Portugal in 1975. Early 1980s droughts displaced approximately 10 000 individuals into extreme poverty, while the civil war commencing in 1981 devastated infrastructure, communication networks, transport networks, displacing over 300 000 people from their homes.⁶⁰ The escalation of conflict in early 2020 further resulted in more than 2,000 civilian deaths and the internal displacement of more than 700,000 individuals, leaving many with lost loved ones and without means to sustain their livelihoods.⁶¹

Similarly, Zimbabwe has experienced prolonged political turmoil since 2000, resulting in loss of many lives, destruction of educational facilities, a sharp decline in healthcare provision and supplies nationwide.⁶² In addition, a series of disruptions caused by corruption among officials further destabilized Zimbabwe's economy.⁶³ Ward argues that political instability sparked an extreme economic crisis, hyperinflation, loss of jobs, and deterioration of health care facilities.⁶⁴ The economic situation caused unemployment exceeding 90 percent across the country.⁶⁵ While Maclean adds that deterioration of public services compounded by external debt crisis also contributed towards economic downfall.⁶⁶

Failure to Collaborate

Loss of Ubuntu principles in the governance of SADC countries has negatively impacted people's livelihoods, further

⁵³ Macassa G, Militao E, Francisco J.D.C, "Is Climate Change Contributing to Food Insecurity and Poor Health Outcomes in Mozambique?" *Austin Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology* 8, no.1 (2021):1-2. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Gloria-Macassa/publication/349120455_Is_Climate_Change_Contributing_to_Food_Insecurity_and_Poor_Health_Outcomes_in_Mozambique/links/60783f7c881fa14b4034120/Is-Climate-Change-Contributing-to-Food-Insecurity-and-Poor-Health-Outcomes-in-Mozambique.pdf

⁵⁴ Edgar Cambaza, Edson Mongo, Elda Anapakala, Robina Nhambire, Jacito Singo, Edsone Machava, "Outbreak of Cholera Due to Cyclone Kenneth in Northern Mozambique, 2019," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16, no. 16, (2019):1-2, <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/16/16/2925>

⁵⁵ "Mozambique Food Security Outlook, February 2023 to September 2023," Relief Web, 9 Mar, 2023. <https://reliefweb.int/report/mozambique/mozambique-food-security-outlook-february-2023-september-2023>

⁵⁶ Ange- Benjamin Brida, Tom Owiyo, Youba Sokona "Loss and Damage From The Double Blow of Flood and Drought In Mozambique," *International Journal of Global Warming* 5, no. 4, (2013):514-516, <https://www.inderscienceonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1504/IJGW.2013.057291>

⁵⁷ Lerato Brown, "Lesotho Declares National Disaster: Food Insecurity Due to El Niño- Induced Drought," World Vision, July 16, 2024, <https://www.wvi.org/stories/global-hunger-crisis/lesotho-declares-national-disaster-food-insecurity-due-el-nino-induced>

⁵⁸ Jasper Veschuur, Sihan Li, Piotr Wolski, Friederike E. L. Otto, "Climate change as a driver of food insecurity in the 2007 Lesotho-South Africa drought," *Scientific Reports* 11, no. 3852(2021):1-2. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-021-83375-x#citeas>

⁵⁹ Elias M. A. Militao, Elsa M. Salvador, Olalekan A. Uthman, Stig Vinberg, Gloria Macassa, "Food Insecurity and Health Outcomes Other than Malnutrition in Southern Africa: A Descriptive Systematic Review," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no.9 (2022):2. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/19/9/5082>

⁶⁰ William Finnegan, *A Complicated War: The Harrowing of Mozambique* (London: University of California Press, 1992), 4-6.

⁶¹ "What can the AU do about the conflict in Mozambique?," PSC Report, 26 March, 2021, <https://issafrica.org/pscreport/psc-insights/what-can-the-au-do-about-the-conflict-in-mozambique>

⁶² Morgan Chitiyo, "Challenges Affecting the Education of Children in Zimbabwe," *Childhood Education* 90, no.6, (2014):415-416, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/00094056.2014.982971?needAccess=true>

⁶³ Charles A Ray, Michael Walsh, "Changing The Status Quo in the US-Zimbabwe Relations," *Science Direct* 68, no. 2, (2024): 190-191, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0030438724000036>

⁶⁴ George F. Ward, *Political Instability in Zimbabwe*, Council on Foreign Relations, 2022

⁶⁵ Chidochashe L. Munangagwa, "The Economic Decline of Zimbabwe," *The Gettysburg Economic Review* 3, no.9, (2009):110, <https://cupola.gettysburg.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1021&context=ger>

⁶⁶ Sandra J Maclean, "Mugabe at War: The political Economy of Conflict in Zimbabwe," *Third World Quarterly* 23, no.3, (2002):513, <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/01436590220138402?needAccess=true>

increasing poverty in the society. Nzimakwe argues that integrating Ubuntu into governance structures of countries ensures that citizens are given a chance to publicly participate in issues concerning their government, as well as promoting transparency in leadership.⁶⁷ Marevesa and Mvengano states that for decades the decline of incorporation of Ubuntu principles in Zimbabwe's governance has contributed to the country's political instability, human rights violations, and corruption culminating in economic collapse under President Robert Gabriel Mugabe's leadership, leaving much of the population in extreme poverty and hardship.⁶⁸

Similarly, Muyingi argues that the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) has suffered prolonged conflict for at least a decade. This ongoing war has led to economic collapse, severe destruction of infrastructure—including schools and healthcare facilities—and exacerbated human suffering, resulting in an increased poverty throughout the community.⁶⁹ These challenges require, key stakeholders—including civil society, the judiciary, politicians, religious authorities and traditional institutions—should engage in dialogue focused on nation-building values rooted in Ubuntu, such as cooperation, forgiveness, and unity as foundational elements for supporting sustainable national development.⁷⁰

Comparative Analysis of Poverty in Southern Africa

Poverty in the Southern African region varies from one country to another. Hence, it is important to analyse how countries in the Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) deal with poverty. A World Bank report states that Botswana is regarded as a growth success story, attributing its stable upper-middle-income status to an abundance of natural resources and strong institutional frameworks.⁷¹ Botswana was once considered one of the world's poorest countries, but has since established a strong record of political stability and economic growth. As a result, its governance is now ranked among the best in Africa, with other countries looking to Botswana as a model for effective governance and development.⁷²

Magombeyi and Odhiambo argue that despite Botswana being one of the countries in Africa which experience fast economic growth and development, poverty is still a major concern in the country due to factors such as unemployment, shortage of health-care professionals, and over reliance on the mining industry, specifically the depletion of diamond reserves, may limit their ability to support poverty reduction programs in the future.⁷³ Therefore, it is important for the country to formulate sustainable policies towards poverty reduction.⁷⁴

According to a report by the United Nations Development Programme, South Africa is classified as an upper-middle-income country, yet it continues to face poverty-related challenges typically found in low-income nations. Inequality remains a significant issue, with the Gini coefficient rising from 0.59 in 1993 to 0.63 in 2019—a trend likely exacerbated by the pandemic. Furthermore, South Africa's unemployment rate remains high at 34.9 percent, with youth aged 15–24 and 25–34 particularly affected.⁷⁵

Msweli argues that although South Africa and Botswana share several similarities, both countries were once colonised by Britain and later on emerged to be upper middle income countries. Msweli further posit that despite the similarities, the countries have certain differences in terms of population size, economic performance, and human development index.⁷⁶ Additionally, a report by Statistics Botswana indicates that Botswana has an estimated population of 2,346,179,⁷⁷ while South Africa's population is estimated at 63 million.⁷⁸ As a result, the population difference plays a significant role in poverty patterns for both Botswana and South Africa.

Global Context of Poverty and Regional Economic Blocs

⁶⁷ T I, Nzimakwe, "Practicing Ubuntu and Leadership for Good Governance: The South African Dialogue" *African Journal of Public Affairs* 7, no.4 (2014):39.

⁶⁸ Batrice Okreye-Manu, Stephen Nkansah Morgan, Ovett Nwosimiri, *Contemporary Development Ethics from an African Perspective: Selected Readings* (Cham: Springer, 2023), 243

⁶⁹ Mbangu Anicet Muyingi, "African Ethics and Moral Possibilities of Ubuntu Towards Conflict Resolution in the Republic of Congo (DRC)," *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences* 4, no.3(2013):566. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/09ac/381a6fa111b61dc3ac5e319da5390a8f37a7.pdf>

⁷⁰ Okreye-Manu, Morgan and Nwosimiri, *Contemporary Development Ethics*, 251.

⁷¹ Carolina Diaz-Bonilla, Baez Ramirez, Javier Eduardo, Buckley Thomas Sanchez Luis Alvaro, Babatshi Gasha, Tshepho Alvaro, Botswana - Systematic Country Diagnostic Update : At a Crossroads - Reigniting Efficient and Inclusive Growth (English), (Washington D.C : World Bank, 2023), <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/099112023112034378/BOSIB056106b900660a7d8068fe9cad99f2>

⁷² *Botswana - Systematic Country Diagnostic Update*, 2.

⁷³ Mercy T, Magombeyi ,Nicholas M, Odhiambo, "Poverty Dynamics in Botswana: Policies, Trends and Challenges," *Cogent Social Sciences* 3,(2017):2. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epdf/10.1080/23311886.2017.1329246?needAccess=true>

⁷⁴ Magombeyi, Odhiambo, "Poverty Dynamics in Botswana," 3.

⁷⁵ UNDP Annual Report 2021 South Africa (UNDP, 2021), https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/2022-09/UNDP%20RSA%20Annual%20Report_2021.pdf

⁷⁶ Pumela Msweli, "Human capital development: what can South Africa learn from Botswana? ," *Environmental Economics Volume* 6, no. 1(2015): 144. https://openscholar.dut.ac.za/bitstream/10321/1581/1/Msweli_EE_Vol_6_01_2015.pdf

⁷⁷ "Botswana population on the decline," Statistics Botswana, May 13, 2022, <https://www.statsbots.org/bw/botswana-population-decline>

⁷⁸ "South Africa's Population Surpasses The 63 million Mark," stats sa, July 30, 2024, <https://www.statssa.gov.za/?p=17430>

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Globally poverty has had a profound impact, severely disrupting the livelihoods of many people in various countries.⁷⁹ However, Alex and others argue that for decades, the global struggle against the multifaceted phenomenon has been defined by various factors. Although rapid economic growth in emerging economies has lifted many out of extreme poverty, driven by fast economic growth in emerging economies, there still exists the constant and troubling reality of continuous social, political, economic, and climate issues, causing the prevalence of poverty in society.⁸⁰ Martuscelli argues that rapid economic growth became possible through the formation of regional economic blocs across the world, which has played a pivotal role in making poverty reduction and advancement of development achievable.⁸¹ The formation of these blocs represents a critical milestone, signifying regional integration as a strategic mechanism for addressing poverty on a global scale.⁸²

Factors Influencing Global Poverty in the Post-Cold War Era

Onslow states that the Post-Cold War era marks the end of the Cold War, which rigorously impacted the development of many countries across the world as a result of proxy wars that took place, particularly in developing countries. In this regard, after the Cold War came to an end, many countries worked hard towards resuscitating their economies to ensure improved livelihood of people.⁸³ However, Jones additionally points out that despite the end of the Cold War, poverty continues to pose a problem for many countries in the post-Cold War era.⁸⁴

Corruption and Weak Governance

Corruption and weak governance constitute critical barriers to socio-economic development of countries in Southern Africa. This substantially contributed to the rapidly rising levels of poverty. Despite notable efforts to promote growth democratic governance, economic growth and political stability, these countries have been reluctant to utilise their policies and practices pertaining to corruption problems.⁸⁵ Political leaders frequently implicated in corrupt practices, including the mismanagement of public funds. Resources allocated development projects are often diverted for personal gain, undermining efforts to advance government initiatives aimed at advancing public welfare.⁸⁶

Additionally, corruption frequently arises during the awarding of government contracts, as tenders are often granted based on personal connections or through bribery involving government officials.⁸⁷ Consequently, many countries in Southern Africa have encountered challenges in implementing effective poverty reduction strategies, leaving a significant portion of the SADC population trapped in poverty. Corruption also contributes to shortages of essential medicines in hospitals, undermining healthcare delivery. Consequently, chronic diseases continue to claim many lives. Conditions such as HIV/AIDS have become increasingly difficult to control, with high rates of infection and reinfection further elevating mortality rates across communities.⁸⁸ Supporting this, a report by UNICEF identifies Southern Africa as the global epicentre of HIV/AIDS. This underscores the ongoing prevalence of HIV/AIDS among families, adolescents, and children throughout societies in the region.⁸⁹

Digital Inequality

In the post-Cold War era, the technological advancement has become a determinant of socio-economic development of countries. Therefore, the socio-economic growth of countries heavily relies on how various economies have managed to adapt smart technologies into their governance structures, institutions, and across the industry at large.⁹⁰ Thus, countries that leverage digital tools and smart technology are often better equipped to manage poverty-related problems through improved service delivery and enhanced productivity. In this regard, the incorporation of smart technology in the agriculture sector, schools, hospitals, and Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is significant for

⁷⁹ Mitchel Chossudovsky, *Organizational Studies: Critical Perspective on Business and Management* (London: Routledge, 2001), 77.

⁸⁰ Alex Hou Hong Ng, Abdul Ghani Farinda, Fock Kui Kan, Ai Ling Lim, Teo Ming Ting, "Poverty: Its Causes and Solutions," *International Journal of Business, Human and Social Sciences* 7, no. 8 (2013): 2471-2472.

⁸¹ Antonio Martuscelli, "Regional Intergration and Poverty: A Review of The Transmission Channels and The Evidence," *Journal of Economic Surveys* 33, no. 2 (2018): 431-433. <https://repository.up.ac.za/server/api/core/bitstreams/a6d9fa7b-cdc1-44ad-bf55-d61db55e35f4/content>

⁸² Martuscelli, "Regional Intergration and Poverty," 434.

⁸³ Sue Onslow, *Cold War in Southern Africa: White Power, Black Liberation* (New York: Routledge, 2009), 2-9.

⁸⁴ Gareth Stedman Jones, *An End to Poverty? : A Historical Debate* (New York: Colombia University Press, 2004), 2.

⁸⁵ Fortune Ganda, "The Influence of Corruption on Environmental Sustainability in The Developing Economies of Southern Africa," *Heliyon* 6, (2020): 1-2. [https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440\(20\)31231-7](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440(20)31231-7)

⁸⁶ Fortune Ganda, "The Influence of Corruption on Environment Sustainability in the Developing Economies of Southern Africa" *Heliyon* 6 (2020): 1. <https://www.cell.com/action/showPdf?pii=S2405-8440%2820%2931231-7>

⁸⁷ Natasha Georgieva Hadji Krsteski, "Corruption in South Africa: Genesis and Outlook" *Journal of Process Management-New Technologies, International* 5, no. 4 (2017): 49. <https://aseestant.ceon.rs/index.php/jouproman/article/view/15160/5733>

⁸⁸ Laetitia C Rispel, Peter de Jager, Sharon Fonn, "Exploring Corruption in the South African Health Sector" *Health Policy* 31, (2016): 239.

⁸⁹ "HIV and AIDS," UNICEF, 2016, <https://www.unicef.org/esa/hiv-and-aids>

⁹⁰ T.W Oshikoya, M.Nureldon Hussain, "Information Technology and the Challenge of Economic Development in Africa," *African Development Review* 10, no. 1 (1998): 101. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/j.1467-8268.1998.tb00099.x>

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fostering inclusive growth. However, a report by the World Bank states that the majority of Sub-Saharan African countries have yet to fully adopt smart technologies; hence poverty is prevalent across the region.⁹¹ Service delivery remains slow in many SADC countries, with the region lagging in internet coverage and accessibility. Currently estimates suggest that only about 4% of the population in Southern Africa is internet users, highlighting significant digital disparities that further constrain economic development.⁹²

Climate Change

Kavalski argues that in the post-Cold War era, environmental degradation has emerged as a critical threat to human survival. As a result, the climate crisis is now recognized as a “real crisis” – a term historically reserved for armed conflict.⁹³ Charles, Kalikoski and Macnaughton posit that poverty in the post-Cold War period is caused by factors pertaining to the geographical location of countries. Hence, the end of superpower rivalry was accompanied by a surge in multilateralism, leading to the establishment of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in 1992, followed by the Kyoto Protocol (1997) and the Paris Agreement in 2015. Indeed, these developments signify the growing importance of climate diplomacy in shaping global responses to both environmental and developmental challenges in post- Cold War era.⁹⁴

Africa suffers the effects of climate change , hence Middleton, O’Keefe, and Moyo argue that despite the continent’s status as the least emitting greenhouse gases, countries within the continent inclusive of those in Southern Africa region find themselves on the brink of poverty due to extreme weather events such as global warming, El Niño, floods, wildfires and droughts.⁹⁵ This situation has left communities and societies in a vulnerable state, with healthcare facilities, schools, and other infrastructure frequently damaged or destroyed by extreme weather events. Climate change has had a particularly severe impact on the agricultural sector, resulting in ongoing food crises.⁹⁶ Floods devastate crop yields, while rising temperatures lead to prolonged droughts.⁹⁷

Regional Economic Blocs – Learning from ASEAN and EU

The operation of regional economic blocs gained momentum after the Cold War as a means to promote economic growth, particularly in underdeveloped countries around the world.⁹⁸ Mirza and other scholars point out that regional integration has played a significant role in global poverty reduction, as evidenced by the successes of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) regional bloc which has made substantial progress in eradicating poverty in the developing world. Through targeted initiatives including including attracting foreign direct investment (FDI), ASEAN has achieved notable progress in reducing poverty across its member states.⁹⁹ Hence, Azania and Sihaloho argue that foreign direct investment is vital in contributing towards the successful development and economic growth of countries, as it is significant in lowering poverty levels in the society.¹⁰⁰ FDI comprises other features which contribute significantly towards poverty reduction, such as improving corporate governance, creating jobs, boosting productivity in the host countries and improving local skills.¹⁰¹ Figure 1 illustrates foreign direct investment across various types of economies.

Figure 1: Foreign Direct Investment in Different Economies

⁹¹ “Digital Transformation Drives Development in Africa,” World Bank18,2024, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2024/01/18/digital-transformation-drives-development-in-afe-afw-africa>

⁹² “ICT and Telecommunications,” Southern African Development Community,2022, <https://www.sadc.int/pillars/ict-telecommunications>

⁹³ Emilian Kavalski, “From the Cold War to Global Warming: Observing Complexity in IR,” *Political Studies Review*9,no.1-2(2011): 6. <chrome://downloads/kavalski-2010-from-the-cold-war-to-global-warming-observing-complexity-in-ir.pdf>

⁹⁴ Anthony Charles, Daniela Kalikoski, Alison Macnaughton, Addressing the Climate Change and Poverty Nexus: A Coordinated Approach in the 2030 Agenda and Paris Agreement(Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations,2019), <https://openknowledge.fao.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/660e26d3-86f3-459f-80fc-da06d7a5bc38/content>

⁹⁵ Neil Middleton, Phil O’Keefe, Sam Moyo , The tears of the Crocodile: From Rio to Reality in the Developing World(London: Pluto Press,1993),29-31.

⁹⁶ Michael E Meadows, “Global Change and Southern Africa,” *Geographical Research*44,no2 (2006):135-145. <chrome://downloads/Geographical%20Research%20-%202006%20-%20MEADOWS%20-%20Global%20Change%20and%20Southern%20Africa.pdf>

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ Sanen Marshall, “A Systematic Perspective on Regional Integration After the End of the Cold War,” *Asia Europe Journal*3,no.3(2005):347-348. <https://link.springer2022..com/article/10.1007/s10308-005-0022-6>

⁹⁹ Hafiz Mirza,Axèle Giroud,Hossein Jalilian,John Weiss,Nick Freeman ,Mya Than, Regionalisation, Foreign Direct Investment and Poverty Reduction: The Case of ASEAN (University of Bradford), https://d1wqtxtslxzle7.cloudfront.net/47756627/Regionalisation_Foreign_Direct_Investmen20160803-11185-1j95ck3-libre.pdf?1470232106=&response-content-disposition=inline%3B+filename%3DRegionalisation_Foreign_Direct_Investmen.

¹⁰⁰ Shania Puteri Azaria, Estro Dariatno Sihaloho, Impacts Of Foreign Direct Investment On Poverty Eradication In Asean-5 Countries, *Economic Journal Trikonomika*20,no.2(December 2021):62. <https://journal.unpas.ac.id/index.php/trikononika/article/view/4085/2049>

¹⁰¹ Azaria, Sihaloho, “Impacts of Foreign Direct Investment,” 63.

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Source: Based on data from UNCTAD statistics; <https://unctadstat.unctad.org>

Since its establishment in 1967, ASEAN has successfully integrated its markets among ASEAN Member States (AMEs) and with other countries and regions. This integration has promoted growth in regional activities, largely through foreign direct investment from multinational companies. In this regard, ASEAN countries have achieved success in attracting foreign investment through an increase in FDI flow since 2016, while in 2018, FDI hiked up to \$155 billion despite the declining trend in global FDI.¹⁰² Moreover, Mirza and colleagues argue that governments play a crucial role in ensuring the successful development and prosperity of their people.¹⁰³

The European Union (EU) has played a significant role in poverty reduction across European countries. The table below outlines the poverty reduction strategies employed by the ASEAN and European Union regional blocs.

Table 1: Regional Blocs and Key Features of Poverty Reduction Strategies

Regional Blocs	Key Features of Poverty Reduction Strategies
ASEAN	<p>a) Diplomatic partnerships and Knowledge exchange</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • China-ASEAN cooperation to provide knowledge exchange in agriculture as a way to give technical training in agriculture to communities.¹⁰⁴ • China-ASEAN cooperation in plays an important role in infrastructure development across ASEAN region. • Cooperation between ASEAN and China on rural development to eradicate poverty. • ASEAN-China cooperation on disaster management.
EUROPEAN UNION	<p>b) Establishment of European Union single market.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing free movement of people • Universal health care for people across the Europe Union member state countries. • unemployment benefits for citizens • Subsidised housing particularly for low income families. <p>b) Establishment of European Union single market.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing free movement of people between EU member state countries as a way to further promote trade as well as ensuring that people have access to a larger pool of jobs and opportunities in the region. <p>c) “Race to bottom”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lowering wages and taxes for the population in order to attract investors • Adjustment of worker protection laws to attract investors.

¹⁰² “ASEAN Investment Report 2017: Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Zones in ASEAN”, 64.

¹⁰³ “ASEAN Investment Report 2017: Foreign Direct Investment and Economic Zones in ASEAN”.

Table 1 show that ASEAN's approach towards poverty reduction is mainly driven by partnership and development-oriented, emphasizing capacity building and regional integration. The regional bloc has adopted China as its main trading partner, strongly relying on agriculture and infrastructure, as China plays a significant role in financing projects. On the other hand, the European Union has opted to adopt a more institutionalised, welfare-oriented and integrated market approach. The EU strategy of adopting market integration and social welfare allows the regional bloc to extend opportunities to all member states within the region and further achieve poverty reduction.

In this regard, both ASEAN and EU regional blocs are important for SADC to benchmark and get some lessons to incorporate in its own policies targeting poverty reduction. For example, ASEAN's infrastructure development depicts how connectivity relevantly reduces poverty by improving aspects on trade, efficiency, market access, and rural-urban linkages, while on the other hand, the EU's approaches towards poverty reduction can easily be integrated into the SADC Free Trade Area (FTA) and also facilitate SADC to formulate policies addressing unemployment and income inequality within the member states. However, the aim is not about replicating both ASEAN and EU models but rather developing relational.

ASEAN's development model aligns with capability approach because investments in agriculture, infrastructure, and technical training enhance people's productive capacities. Rural development initiatives empower individuals to participate more fully in economic life. In parallel, Ubuntu's communal principles encourage policies that prioritise social cohesion and collective well-being over pure market efficiency.

Conclusion

Since its establishment in 1992 the SADC regional bloc has implemented policies and strategies to reduce poverty and improve people's livelihoods across the region. The Southern African Development Community comprises countries with a shared history of liberation struggles against colonization. A majority of countries in Southern Africa are immersed in a vicious cycle of poverty, therefore causing the prevalence of poverty due to factors pertaining to colonial legacies, corruption, digital inequality, climate change and failure to collaborate (loss of Ubuntu). Historical and political factors, including civil wars and political instability, have also contributed to persistent poverty in the region. This article avails an overview of the factors contributing to poverty, from a global perspective down to Southern Africa. The research also highlights how poverty remains prevalent in the post-Cold War era due to issues such as corruption, digital inequality, climate change, and loss of Ubuntu. Moreover, as a way to address poverty the study points out how regional integration has played an important role in alleviating poverty across many countries. Regional blocs like the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and the European Union have been instrumental in driving economic development. Initiatives such as foreign direct investment have facilitated poverty reduction in Southeast Asian countries—a strategy that SADC could adopt to advance development in Southern Africa.

Historical and political factors, including civil wars and political instability, have contributed to persistent poverty in the region. For example, the civil war in Mozambique severely damaged the country's economy and negatively affected people's livelihoods. Notably, the effects of poverty are also evident in countries like Botswana and South Africa, despite their status as upper-middle-income economies with high Human Development Index rankings within Southern Africa.

Climate change has emerged as a major threat to development of many countries across Southern Africa region, exacerbating food insecurity, hunger, and vulnerability. Countries such as Botswana and Mozambique have experienced adverse effects of climate variability, including droughts and floods, which disrupt agricultural production and livelihoods. These environmental challenges deepen poverty and strain governmental capacity to respond effectively. In this manner SADC ought to formulate policies to address climate change and food insecurity in the region. In this manner, through the introduction of new farming technologies and improved market access for small-scale agriculture food insecurity crisis would be addressed.

As final observation the study highlights that integrating Ubuntu into governance structures of SADC member states would significantly allow citizens to have a chance to publicly participate in issues concerning governance, as well as promoting transparency in leadership, subsequently leading sustainable development of the SADC region at large.

¹⁰⁵ Laping Wu, "Trade Facilitation and Poverty Reduction: China-ASEAN Region Case Study," Working paper no.135 (Asia-Pacific Research and Training Network on Trade, October, 2013), 3-14. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/103859/1/771759134.pdf>

¹⁰⁶ Chrysa Leventi, Holly Sutherland, Iva Valentinova Tasseva, "Improving Poverty Reduction in Europe: What Works Best Where?," *Journal of European Social Policy* 29,no.1(2018):29-32, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/epub/10.1177/0958928718792130>
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